

A Study on Brand Positioning of Ramraj Cotton

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Abstract

Brand and package are two associated attributes of a product. Both are important and integral attributes for the success of any product. Adequate attention on Branding is essential as it is perceived by consumers as intrinsic part of the product and add Value to the product. For example a bottle of 'Parachute' hair oil is understood as at high quality, expensive one. But the same presented in an unmarked bottle would be viewed as, lower in quality even though the oil is identical. Branding is the act of naming a product of for its identification and distinction form that of competitors. The marketer can build up a bright image of his organization around the brand. It enables national advertisement of a specific product and it is pre-sold through advertising. Branded product can be easily recognized by the customer in the retail shop. It offers protection to the consumer as it identifies the firm behind the product. Branding enables the firm assured control over the market. Repeat sales are stimulated and product substitution is not possible. It creates an exclusive market for the product. When brands are successfully and effectively promoted, the very existence of the middleman depends upon a continued supply of each brand.

Introduction

Brand Positioning

Brand/product positioning is what you do to the mind of the prospect. That is you create and build up brand equity, which is the perceived value of the product position in the minds of consumers. The core thought behind positioning is the idea that your brand/product must occupy a particular space continuously in the consumer's mind. It is called 'renting mind space', i.e., finding a suitable space in that mind and sit on it and do not let someone else (rival) to dislodge. Positioning is based on some Unique Selling Proposition (USP). It may be some unique feature of the product, some unique feature of the market or some feature of the competition which becomes the core idea and around that feature the product/brand is placed in the market. Brand positioning answers the question who am I and what is in me? By answering this question marketer can clearly differentiate his product/brand. Great Shake, Soyamilk is positioned as a health drink. Complian an is positioned as a health builder. Amul milk powder (the milkman) is positioned as a convenient and a ready substitute to milk. Limca is positioned as a thirst quenching softdrink. Rasna is positioned on economy and convenience. Surf is positioned on quality 'High power Surf, washes whitest'. Vimal fabrics are positioned on

fashion for fashion-loving ad well-to-so market. Maruti car is positioned on fuel efficiency. Thus, we have some unique selling proposition for positioning, e.g., luxury, distinctiveness, convenience, novelty, usage etc. Loyalty decision by the consumer is based on many considerations, value (price and quality), image (both the brand's own personality and its reputation), convenience, fashion, ease of availability, satisfaction, service, economy, guarantee, warranty, and so on. Savy marketer must build brand equity to create sustained brand position or space in the consumer mind-set. Note: Positioning is a policy document and is sacrosanct as the Geeta and should not be tampered with. Promises must be guaranteed by the marketer to ensure 'renting mind space'. Let marketers in India realize this.

Objectives of the Study

1. To find the positioning of Ramraj Cotton .
2. To know the influence the brand Ramraj Cotton.
3. To find channel of distribution of Ramraj Cotton brand.

Scope of the Study

1. The study highlights the importance of brand RAMRAJ cotton awareness in DHARMAPURI DISTRICT.
2. The common problem faced by consumer were also highlighted study.
3. It also provides certain remedial measures to eradicate the problem and to improve the importance of brand RAMRAJ cotton awareness.

Statement of the Problems

The Ramraj Cotton brand manufacturing industry in India is growing and expanding the number and different brand in the marketing so the researcher decide to study the different brand preference to Ramraj brand consumer at a particular area known their degree of satisfaction level.

To examine the common feature and different feature among the different model in Ramraj Cotton Brand.

Research Methodology

A system of models, process and techniques used to find the results of a research problem is called a research methodology.

Research Design

A search design is a plan of action out in connection with a proposed research work. It is the blue print of the proposed study.

Area of the Study

The study carried out in Dharmapuri District.

Source of Data

There are two types of data using in this study.

1. Primary Data
2. Secondary Data

Primary Data

It refers to information that is generated to meet the specific requirements of the investigation at hand. Primary data is known as the data collected for the first time through field survey.

Secondary Data

Secondary data refers to the information or facts already collected. Such data are collected with the objective of understanding the past status of any variable.

Tools of the Study

Percentage Analysis

Percentage Analysis

Percentage analysis refers to a special types of ratio. Percentage is used in making comparison between two percentage analysis two or more series of data

Review of Literature

Introduction

Reviewing the literatures, such as books, published articles and reports relevant to the study is much importance as it would provide the reader an in- depth view about various aspects underlying present research work.

Ries and Trout (1985)¹ Other marketing literatures brand positioning in contributing to the success of a brand. Distinctiveness is defined as the degree to which the consumer perceives that a brand is distinct from it, competitors. A brand can have a price premium if it is perceived as being different from its competitors.

Zeithaml (1988)² Perceived quality is the customer's about a product's overall excellence or superiority that is different from objective quality. Objective quality refers to the technical and verifiable nature of products/service, processes and quality controls. E.g. brand name, quality, price, store, product information.

De Chernatony and Mc William (1989)³ Functional brand are the tangible features of a product. While evaluating a brand, consumers link the performance of the functional to the brand

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Gender of the Respondents

S.No.	Gender	No of Respondent	Percentage (%)
1.	Male	17	57%
2.	Female	13	43%
Total		30	100

Source: Primary data

Interpretation

The above table 4.1 shows gender of the respondents out of 30 respondents in that,57% of the respondents are belonging to the female,43% of the respondents are belonging to the male.

Majority (57%) of the respondents are belonging to the male

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- 1 Ries, Al and Trout, Jack (1985), "Challenges and opportunities facing brand management:An introduction to special issue", journal of marketing research 31:149-158.
 - 2 Zeithaml, V.A. (1988), "Consumer perceptions of price, quality, and value: a means-end model and synthesis of evidence", journal of marketing 52(3): 2-22.
 - 3 DeChernatony, L. And Mc William G. (1989), "The varying nature of brands as asset", International journal of advertising 8: 339-49.

Respondents Opinion about Using Ramraj Cotton

S.No	Opinion	No of Respondents	Percentage (%)
1	Yes	18	60
2	No	12	40
Total		30	100

Source: Primary Data

Interpretation

The table 4.2 show that the opinion regarding using ramraj cotton out of 30 respondents (60%) of the respondents are using ramraj cotton and remaining (40%) of the respondents are using other brand.

Majority (60%) of the respondents are opinion regarding using ramraj cotton.

Respondents Opinion about Goog Brand Position

S.No	Opinion Good Brand Position	No.of Respondents	Percentage (%)
1.	Yes	Yes	70%
2.	No	No	30%
Total		30	100

Interpretation

The table 4.3 shows that the respondents opinion about good brand out 30 of respondents 70% of the respondents are said Ramraj cotton brand position and remaining 30% of the respondents are said not good brand position

Majority (70%) of the respondents have providing a Ramraj cotton

Finding

1. Majority (60%) of the respondents are opinion regarding using ramraj cotton.
2. Majority (57%) of the respondents are belonging to the male
3. Majority (70%) of the respondents have providing a Ramraj cotton

Suggestions

1. To give some more importance to the various promotional techniques through different medias.
2. By giving importance to the consumers feedback.
3. Make the customer delighted by having a good customer relationship.
4. The branding techniques should be changing according to the market trends.

Conclusion

Marketing plans a pivotal in the development of our country the development of marketing haw always kept face with the economic growth of country. Now in the modern marketing faced the high competition in their activities.

The company ensures its advertisement, like more customer service, and buyers about better life style. The company uses a variety of Ramraj cotton .They start with a basic appeal, which is the main selling point, than the other theme of an advertisement. Are simply conveying a persuasive message reached the public area from this analysis we concluded that the advertisements has to reach the customers in satisfaction and opinion of the Brand quality product.